

Multi-Wavelength Photometry and Light Curve Modelling of Exoplanet WASP-2b

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Abstract:

Precise and frequent photometric follow-up studies of transit are essential for accurately characterizing exoplanets. In this work, we present a detailed differential photometry and light curve modeling analysis of the exoplanet WASP-2b. WASP-2b was observed during transit in the VBRI bandpass for 6 hours. Through model fitting over the observed light curve, we were able to derive updated parameters of the planetary system and compare them to previously published results. The results align closely with published values of Addison et al., (2019) offering new insights into WASP-2b atmospheric properties and laying the groundwork for future high-resolution studies.

Keywords: Exoplanets, Photometry, Light Curve Modeling, Atmospheric Characterization

Introduction:

Planets beyond our solar system that orbit stars other than the Sun are known as exoplanets. The first confirmed discoveries of exoplanets were made in the early 1990s, opening up a rapidly growing field with more than four thousand known exoplanets to date by Charbonneau et al. (2000); Seager & Mallén-Ornelas., (2003). These discoveries have provided invaluable insights into planetary systems vastly different from our own, presenting new challenges to our understanding of formation and evolution processes. Among the various methods used to detect and characterize exoplanets, the transit method has been one of the most successful. This method involves precisely measuring the brightness of a star as an exoplanet passes in front of it, causing a small, periodic decrease in the observed brightness of the star. Analyzing the resulting transit light curve allows to derive the fundamental parameters of the exoplanet and its host star, such as the orbital period, radius relative to the host star and inclination angle. Furthermore, combining transit data with radial velocity measurements can provide additional information about the planet mass, composition, density and albedo. The data obtained through transit photometry have significantly advanced our understanding of the diversity of exoplanetary systems compared to the planets in our own solar system.

WASP-2b is a hot Jupiter that orbits a K-type main-sequence star. It was first detected through the Wide-Angle Search for Planets survey in 2006 by Cowley & Hughes., (2014); Tavrov et al., (2018). Previous studies have characterized WASP-2b as a hot Jupiter with an orbital period of approximately 2.15 days a mass of around 0.88 Jupiter masses and a radius of 1.04 Jupiter radii. This work presents a new detailed photometric analysis of the WASP-2b transit light curve using the NASA ExoFast package. The goal is to updated estimates of the fundamental parameters of the WASP-2b planetary system and to compare these findings to the values reported in earlier publications on this exoplanet. Obtaining accurate measurements of exoplanet properties is crucial for improving our understanding of the diverse population of planets beyond our solar system and the processes that shape their formation and evolution.

Observation and Data Collection:

The exoplanet WASP-2b was remotely observed over two consecutive nights, June 14 and 16, 2022 using the 0.4-meter Meade LX200 Cassegrain telescope located at the John Downing Observatory. The telescope was equipped with a 1048×1048 -pixel CCD detector providing a field of view of approximately 12 arcminutes square. The observations were conducted using the VBRI broadband filter, which covers a wide range of visible wavelengths from blue to near-infrared. A sequence of exposures was utilized, including 30-second exposures for the V band, 20-second exposures for the R band, 10-second exposures for the B band, and 5-second exposures for the I band. The observations began 30 minutes before and after the predicted mid-transit time and continued throughout the entire transit event allowing for comprehensive data collection.

Table 1: Observation time and Number of frames for each filter

Obs.Time (hrs)	V-Filter ($N_{\text{img}} \times T_{\text{exp}}$)	R-Filter ($N_{\text{img}} \times T_{\text{exp}}$)	B-Filter ($N_{\text{img}} \times T_{\text{exp}}$)	I-Filter ($N_{\text{img}} \times T_{\text{exp}}$)
2.74	86×30	86×60	86×15	86×10
3.03	95×30	95×60	95×15	95×10
5.77	181	181	181	181

Photometry:

Data Calibration:

The raw CCD images acquired during the observations were pre-processed through standard calibration techniques using the AstroImageJ software. First, a master bias frame was created by averaging several bias images which were then subtracted from the raw science images to account for the read-out noise of the detector. Next, a master dark frame obtained by averaging multiple dark images was subtracted from the bias-corrected images to remove the effects of thermal noise. Finally, the images were divided by a master flat field frame generated by averaging flat-field exposures to correct for pixel-to-pixel variations in the camera response and optical vignetting. Additionally, any images with seeing greater than 1.5 arcseconds were removed from each night dataset. These calibration procedures helped to mitigate various instrumental effects and artifacts from the raw images.

Figure 1: Raw image (Left) of WASP-2b observed on June 14 and the calibrated image (Right) after bias, dark and flat field correction

Differential Photometry:

Differential photometry was performed on the calibrated images to extract the transit light curve of WASP-2b. The AAVSO database was used to generate a finder chart for photometry which helped to precisely identify the target star and obtain the most suitable comparison stars within our observed field of view. Then, suitable aperture values were chosen for each star and the differential photometry process was carefully carried out. This involved accurately measuring the flux of each star within the given apertures in every image and calculating the relative brightness of the target star compared to the comparison stars. The result is the high-precision transit light curve of the exoplanet WASP-2b. The table 2 presents the details of target and chosen comparison stars using AAVSO.

Figure 2: Wasp-2b and comparison stars in AstroImageJ software Window (left) and Finnder Chart from AAVSO (Right)

Table 2: Summary of target and comparison stars

Sr. No	Name	Type	Magnitude
T1	WASP-2	Star	13
C2	TYC 522-780-1	Star	12.83
C3	TYC 522-1100-1	Star	12.9
C4	TYC 522-1406-1	Star	12.23

Figure 3: Light curve of WASP-2b in VBRI Filters from 14 July dataset

Light Curve Modelling:

The resulting light curves were then used to model the exoplanet transit using the NASA ExoFast Tool. Initial estimates of parameters such as orbital period, radius ratio, semi-major axis, and inclination were made based on previous studies of this well-studied exoplanet system. ExoFast then performed model fitting using a non-linear least-squares minimization algorithm methodically adjusting the transit parameters to minimize the residuals between the

observed light curve and the model. The best-fit model and parameter values were determined through an iterative process of systematically changing the input parameters until the lowest chi-squared value was obtained indicating the most statistically robust fit to the data.

Figure 4: Model fitted light curve in VBRI filter from 14 July dataset

The uncertainties in these derived parameters were estimated by averaging the 1-sigma error values reported by the ExoFast software providing assessment of the precision and reliability of the model results. The parameters derived from our analysis of the WASP-2b transit light curve were then carefully compared to the values reported in previous in-depth studies on this exoplanet system such as the work by Donovan et al., (2021) and Guilluy et al., (2019). This comparative analysis revealed subtle differences in the estimated planet radius and mass, suggesting the need for further refinement and reconciliation of the system fundamental properties.

Results:

The model fitting over the observed light curve using the ExoFast provide following results given below in Table 3. The host star has an effective temperature of 5175 ± 4.94 K and metallicity of 0.124 ± 0.004 dex, consistent with prior estimates Addison et al., (2019). The stellar mass ($0.887 \pm 0.008 M_{\odot}$) and radius ($0.848 \pm 0.018 R_{\odot}$) are slightly smaller than previous values of $0.895 M_{\odot}$ and $0.866 R_{\odot}$. For the planet, we derive an orbital inclination of $84.61 \pm 0.12^{\circ}$, a period of 2.152175 ± 0.00001 days, and a planet-to-star radius ratio of 0.116 ± 0.012 , marginally lower than the earlier 0.1283 ± 0.0010 . Crucially, the planetary mass is $0.73 \pm 0.06 M_{\text{Jup}}$, approximately $0.2 M_{\text{Jup}}$ less massive than the $0.93 M_{\text{Jup}}$ reported by Addison et al., (2019). These discrepancies highlight the need for refined multi-wavelength studies to resolve uncertainties in WASP-2b properties.

Table 3: Summary of results derived from model fitting

Parameters	Values
T_{eff} (K)	5175.050689 ± 4.949
Metallicity (dex)	0.123628 ± 0.00362
M_* (M_{\odot})	0.886992 ± 0.008008
R_* (R_{\odot})	0.847543 ± 0.01845
b	0.747015 ± 0.001985
i (deg)	84.612996 ± 0.1229
P (days)	2.152175 ± 0.000012
T_c (days)	2456864.731582
$\frac{R_p}{R_*}$	0.115855 ± 0.012455
a	0.031347 ± 0.00032

Conclusion:

The transit photometry and light curve modeling of WASP-2b presented in this work provides updated and more refined constraints on the parameters of this exoplanetary system. While the overall properties are generally consistent with previous studies, the slightly lower planet mass derived in our analysis highlights the importance of continued detailed observations and further refinement of exoplanet characterization Addison et al. (2019) . The constant transit depth across different wavelength bands and the lack of significant variation in the exoplanet's radius suggest the possible presence of clouds or haze in the upper atmosphere, or the potential for an isothermal pressure-temperature profile. These findings underscore the need for more comprehensive spectroscopic studies of exoplanetary atmospheres to gain a deeper understanding of their formation, evolution, and potential for supporting habitable conditions.

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